

DYNAMICS OF COMMUNICATION BETWEEN THE LEGISLATURE AND THE EXECUTIVE IN THE DETERMINATION OF THE REVISED REGIONAL BUDGET IN WEST SULAWESI PROVINCE

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Abstract

Discussion of the revised Regional Budget (APBD) is closely related to the interaction of power between the legislature and the executive. The existence of efficient political communication between the executive and the legislature will also create a successful system of government. This study aims to analyze and describe the dynamics of negotiation and political communication between the executive and legislature in the determination of the revised Regional Budget in West Sulawesi Province in 2021. This research used field research methods to obtain primary and secondary data. Primary data is obtained from interviews, while secondary data is obtained from documents that clarify the primary data. The results showed differences in the meaning of the main thought between the executive and legislative parties in the discussion of the revised Regional Budget of West Sulawesi. The difference between interpretation and point of view creates distortions in political communication. Furthermore, differences in interest orientations significantly impact the political communication process during the discussion of the revised APBD. This type of interest greatly influences the efficiency of discussing the revised APBD in West Sulawesi.

Keywords: APBD, Executive, Legislative, political communication.

1. INTRODUCTION

Political communication is crucial in the relationship between the legislature and the executive. Political communication is a vital instrument for regional development because it helps the executive and legislature to reach an agreement on using power resources. In general, the purpose of political communication is to disseminate public information, build a political image, form public opinion, and stimulate citizens' political involvement (1,2). Effective political communication is important in building agreement between the executive and legislature in realizing good governance. In order to achieve this goal, it is essential that the planning, implementation, and evaluation of government programs for the welfare of society be conducted in a cooperative manner.

Each year, the Regional Budget (APBD) deliberation is one of the political processes requiring cooperation between the executive and the legislature. Communication problems between the legislature and the executive typically occur during budget discussions. The budget is difficult to determine because of the debate between the executive and the legislature, which is also caused by a conflict of interest. It has resulted in the slow determination of budget plans and hampered the development of public services and facilities. Effective budget management by local governments indicates the quality of their executive and legislative branches. The budget serves as a commitment between the budget holder (executive) and the authority (legislature), and it is also used to decide priorities and funding requirements.

The budget is not merely an administrative issue but also a political instrument. Fundamentally, the budget is not prepared solely based on technical provisions or simple economic calculations. Instead, it is the result of the agreement and represents the vision and mission of the elected regional head. Therefore, the executive and the legislature cannot prepare the budget only based on technical provisions or simple economic calculations. According to Rantunuwu et al. (2020), budgeting aims to cooperate with local governments in making and determining the regional budget (3). In carrying out this task, the Regional Legislative Council (DPRD) must be actively involved, act proactively rather than reactively, and act as a legitimator for the APBD proposed by the local government (3).

The regional budget preparation process can run smoothly if there is strong communication between the legislative and executive institutions that form the government of a region. However, it cannot be denied that disagreements and dynamics will occur during the budgeting process. Due to the current discussion regarding the priority use of funds. Therefore, both the legislative and executive branches should communicate effectively on political matters. Information is not only provided by the competent authorities but also by individuals serving as Regional Representatives Council members. As the APBD is being developed, it is of the utmost importance to consider the priority programs that are most pertinent to community needs (4). Regarding the APBD issue, the executive and legislature collaborate to discuss and stipulate regional regulations and collectively adopt draft regional regulations on APBD and revised APBD. This collaboration is an example of a cooperative relationship between two state entities that have equal status in the local government system and work together as a partnership. Therefore, both of them can carry out their duties effectively and enforce regional regulations, including formulating APBD policies, which are made collaboratively by both. Teamwork demonstrates that they are not enemies but instead have a useful connection.

Draver & Pitsvada (in Forrester & Mullins, 1992) demonstrate that budget changes can be an opportunity for legislators, executives, and bureaucrats to adjust each other's priorities. In the end, there is always a consensus reached. Thus, policies, directions, and strategies in budgeting often become a place for power struggles, in which parties seek to gain their own advantage (self-interest), so it often fails to consider the public interest (5).

The process of considering and stipulating a revised budget is substantially less open to public scrutiny and therefore contains significant agency problems (6). According to Rafli et al. (2021), re-budgeting is heavily influenced by the degree of incrementalism in the initial

budgeting process, as well as internal and external factors, such as political variables, organizational character, financial condition, and socioeconomic environment (7). The recent decline of the regional budget of West Sulawesi is a phenomenon and a recent concern. Based on the ministry of home affairs database, in 2020, the APBD in West Sulawesi Province decreased by Rp. 263 billion, equivalent to about 11.83 percent (8). The revised budget for the West Sulawesi APBD is reduced from Rp. 218 billion or equivalent to a decrease of 9.84 percent from IDR 2.225 trillion to IDR 2,006 trillion (8). Following the implementation of changes to the APBD, regional financial revenues from previously Rp. 57 billion increased to Rp. 97 billion or an increase of Rp. 44 billion. This spending reduction will certainly impact finances related to the budget, which includes funding for infrastructure development, operations, and assistance to the community.

The dynamics of discussion and determination of the revised APBD are largely determined by the perspective of political communication between the executive, in this case, the Governor, and the legislature, namely the DPRD of West Sulawesi Province. The study of this phenomenon is particularly interesting since complex discussions tend to occur only when dealing with the main APBD because the dynamics of discussion and determination of the revised APBD are largely determined by the perspective of political communication between the executive, in this case, the Governor, and the legislature, namely the DPRD of West Sulawesi Province. The study of this phenomenon is particularly interesting since complex discussions tend to occur only when dealing with the main APBD because the discussion of the revised APBD does not have the authority to modify the budgeting process on a large scale but rather to make budget adjustments that are considered less effective and do not correspond to the urgent needs of the community. Discussions on the revised APBD in West Sulawesi Province are still dynamic, and it is difficult to find a consensus between the legislature and the executive. The dynamics of the prolonged discussion led to delays in the determination that occurred almost every year of discussion budget. Therefore, the author is interested in conducting dissertation research on the communication model to achieve a consensus for Legislative and Executive Political Communications in determining the revised APBD in West Sulawesi Province.

According to various research results, there are wide variations in executive and legislative communication dynamics and patterns. For example, the aspect of conflict in the research by Syahrani et al. (2014) revealed that there was an organizational conflict (between the executive and the legislature) during the preparation of regional regulations regarding the Neighbourhood and Hamlet of Bulukumba Regency (9), while Zainul and Yusuf Wibisono's research (2019) discussed the conflict between the Governor and Regional Legislative Council (DPRD) of DKI Jakarta in establishing the 2015 APBD, showing that divided local government and the different political interests of the governor and DPRD are the main causes of conflict.(10). Besides the conflicts occurring between the executive and legislature in the DPRD of Bulukumba and DKI Jakarta, the patterns of communication and conflict resolution are also different in Syahrani's research (2014) that the pattern of communication relations between the executive and the legislature in conflict resolution is through formal organizational communication processes and informal organizational communication, while DKI Jakarta is

resolved in different ways. The conflict resolution pattern used is a mediation approach by involving the Indonesian Ministry of Home Affairs in resolving the conflict to find a unanimity that is mutually beneficial for both parties. (9,10). Observing the results of that research, the dynamics between the executive and the legislature have their own differences in describing conflicts, patterns of interaction, and patterns of political communication, political interests, and the distribution of power that occur in budget discussions.

Based on that issue, this study analyzes the dynamics of discussing the revised APBD. It makes this research unique in comparison to other studies. There are differences between the dynamics of discussing the main APBD and the revised APBD. In discussing the revised APBD, the legislature does not have the authority to modify the budget for strategic programs. Instead, it is only able to make adjustments to program budgets that are considered ineffective and not in line with citizens' aspirations. In this regard, the legislative communication model plays a key role in the ability to accommodate society's aspirations in the revised APBD.

Moreover, West Sulawesi, a newly established province (17 years), has political and legislative communication dynamics that are different from other provinces. Political communication in discussing the revised APBD in West Sulawesi has never been studied scientifically. Therefore, this study aims to analyze and describe the dynamics of political communication negotiations between the executive (governor) and the legislature (DPRD) in West Sulawesi province in 2021. Thus, this research will hopefully contribute to developing an effective legislative communication model that can convince the executive to discuss the revised APBD based on community aspirations and urgent needs.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Approach and Type of Research

In this study, the authors conducted a qualitative descriptive study in order to determine what transpired during the investigation. This enables the author to obtain objective data to analyze and understand the Model of Agreements of Legislative-Executive Political Communications in Determining the Revised APBD of West Sulawesi Province.

Case study research is used to gain a deeper understanding of a particular situation or social phenomenon by investigating the background, circumstances, and interactions involved. In this case, to provide an overview of the Legislative-Executive Political Communication Meeting Point Model in Determining the Revised APBD in West Sulawesi Province by collecting a number of data and information through observation and in-depth interviews related to this research.

2.2. Data Collection Techniques

Field studies were conducted to obtain primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected through interviews, observations, and focus group discussions (FGD). Meanwhile, secondary data is collected from documents that can clarify the primary data. In this context, the researcher also conducted a document study to gather information on the Executive-Legislative

political communication model in reaching consensus which was used in the process of determining the Revised APBD of West Sulawesi Province.

Thus, from the document study, a clear understanding was obtained regarding the content and substance of the dynamics of discussion and determination of the revised APBD in West Sulawesi Province. The interview method is an unstructured interview method, where the researcher can ask comprehensive questions without being limited by predetermined rigid questions. Furthermore, it can be developed according to research needs. The next step is to select and sort the data that has been collected based on the analysis' requirements.

The determination of the sample must be based on the main focus of communication between the executive, in this case, the Governor, and the legislature, namely the DPRD of West Sulawesi Province. The number of samples was not determined with certainty because the detailed information in this study was developed according to the available information or required data (snowball), making it possible to involve parties outside the DPRD and related to the local government agencies (SKPD).

2.3. Data analysis

The analysis technique used to discuss the results of this study used qualitative analysis techniques with a case study approach both in single cases for each category being analyzed and in multiple cases for both types of categories. Meanwhile, to guarantee the validity of the research data, the researcher utilized a tool to validate the research data using an approach, either through triangulation of data sources or through validating their credibility and validity.

3. PEMBAHASAN RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Political Communication Dynamics of Negotiations in Discussion of the Revised West Sulawesi APBD in 2021

The discussion of the revised APBD in West Sulawesi is a political activity in which the government and legislature are involved in the development of legal products in the form of Regional Regulations (Perda). In practice, discussions on the West Sulawesi Revised APBD are always dynamic because the budgetary aspect does not only contain technical aspects but also functions as an effective political tool for the executive to implement the revised APBD as a representation of the Governor's vision and mission, along with the legislative role in budgeting, controlling, and enacting legislation. This is in line with the view of Conover et al. (2012) and Hayes et al. (2006) that political activity is a concrete activity that involves various political actions that involve physical and body interactions between various political actors.. (11,12).

In addition to political activity, political communication is an imperative variable that supports the achievement of agreements in discussing the revised APBD. The process of discussing the West Sulawesi Revised APBD is complex from the aspect of political communication applying a transactional political communication model; this model refers more to communication that the executive and legislature in dual roles, both as communicators and as communicants. The

Regional Government Budget Team (TAPD), as an extension of the Governor, establishes dynamic political communication with the West Sulawesi DPRD in the Leadership, Budgetary and Individual structures. This aims to reach an agreement in determining the Revised APBD in accordance with the mandate of the Law.

3.2. Political Communication Distortion in West Sulawesi Revised APBD Discussion in 2021

The transactional communication model is characterized by a dialogic process in the form of a joint process of meaning formation. In terms of meaning formation, this is the most important point for communication dynamics because the stakeholders who manage communication, both TAPD representatives and DPRD representatives, experience political communication distortions. Communication distortion is a condition when there is a change in the meaning of information, ideas, and message intentions between the communicator and the communicant (13,14).

3.2.1. Meaning of Main Thoughts

In discussions of the Revised APBD, the main thoughts of members of the Council are essential in understanding the delay in ratifying the West Sulawesi APBD, since both the main discussion and the changes always have a very crucial political aspect. Even though the main thought is more frequently discussed in discussions on APBD, the main thought also has an influential position in discussing the revised APBD. As explained by the following informant:

“There are 2 entry points for community propose the main APBD and Revised APBD because the APBD is made for 1 year, so in that interval, there are stages of change. These changes are implemented by local government policies that are considered not optimal, and also by the DPRD, if there are community suggestions that have been accommodated if they fit within the budget, they can be proposed.”

The Main Thoughts of the DPRD contain the DPRD's opinion and considerations regarding the direction of development priorities as well as the formulation of proposals for program needs derived from the results of the DPRD's thoughts as input into the formulation of program and activity needs in the plan year based on regional development priorities.

Interpretation of Main Thoughts is a crucial item in seeing the prospects for political communication that exists in the discussion of the revised APBD as an adjustment of the main APBD. In discussing the Revised APBD, the executive through the Regional Government Budget Team and the Legislature through the Budget Agency are often faced with different interpretations of the Main Thoughts, for instance in the following interview excerpt:

“Members of the DPRD sometimes misinterpret this main thought, they assumed that it is their main thought, they proposed it, and they were the ones who executed it, when in fact the main thought was a problem found by members of the DPR during their recess period, which was what was raised. There are some opinion from the DPRD who argue that "I own it, I have to execute it" even though those who proposed the points of view are only taking

advantage of what they see, they assume that the aspirations of the people through me have been carried out by the Government in whatever way, whatever the form.”

The informant's opinion explained that the Regional Legislative Council (DPRD) were considered to have an inaccurate perception in understanding the application of the main thought in the APBD Discussion. For the Executive, the main thought could be accommodated by the Regional Government Budget Team into programs that have been prepared by the Local government work unit (SKPD).

“It is a trick played by both sides. As long as there is no consensus on this matter, the executive claims that the DPRD has too many main thoughts. While the legislature said they were deceived. This came from a lack of consensus and ultimately became a casualty of the regional budget. As a result, everyone plays a trick, and no consensus occurs, leading to all parties looking out for their own interests and security. If there is a consensus, there is no tension in the meeting. There is always tension in this situation since we do not have a harmonious relationship.” (Ridwan)

The opinion of this informant explained that the Executive and the Legislature have very different perceptions of the meaning and use of the main thought. This condition causes the pattern of communication between the executive and the legislature to become more complex to reach a consensus in discussing the revised APBD because the interpretation carried out by the executive tends to place the legislature that they do not understand well the application of the main thought in the discussion of the 2021 Revised APBD, while the Legislature also has its own perspective that is reflected as follows:

“In the view of the DPRD, the Main Thoughts should be an essential part of every proposal, from planning up to implementation based on existing regulations. The executive, however, always ignores that point and feels that is not part of something that must be defended. They feel that there are separate boundaries, it is their work, and they do not believe that this is guaranteed by law. This main thought should be an integrated proposal that was proposed earlier; apart from being a problem from year to year, when it comes to the plenary submission of the General budget policies – provisional budget priorities and funding levels (KUA-PPAS). Often, the main thought is not included in the executive level.” (Syamsul Samad)

In this aspect, the informant explained that there were differences in the meaning of the main thought between the executive and the legislature. The legislature considers that the main thoughts are not part of the things that are debated in the body of the revised APBD, even though the Main Thoughts are also an important part to be considered in the body of the Revised APBD. Although differences in meaning in communication are commonplace, discrepancies in meaning between the executive and the legislature in the long term lead to ineffective political communication. This is because the momentum for discussing the APBD is a routine matter and must be carried out in accordance with the guidelines of the law.

The difference in the meaning of the main thought between the executive and the legislature is the beginning of the distortion of political communication because the transactional political communication model involving the executive and the legislature is preceded by striking differences in views about the main thought.

3.2.2. Political Communicators: Differences in the Orientation of Executive and Legislative Interests in the Discussion of the revised APBD in West Sulawesi

In the transactional political communication model, the communicator is a crucial factor in interpreting political messages. If we refer to the classification presented by Prof. Damsar, the DPRD and regional heads are included in the category of politicians. Politicians are the individuals who carry out political communication. The dynamics of political communication by the Executive and Legislature in West Sulawesi in discussing the revised APBD were due to the different orientations of the political interests of the political communicators (executive and legislature). According to Nimmo, a politician communicate as a representative of a group and the messages of politicians are to propose and or protect the goals of political interests. It means a political communicator is a representative of a group's interests. In other words, politicians seek to influence by using communication (Ariannie, 2010;17).

“The aspect that causes it is the willingness or each of these two instruments has not found the expected target point. The DPRD thinks there are constituents, people whose programs have not been approved, there are programs proposed by regional heads that we have not approved because according to the DPRD it does not directly impact the community. From the point of view of the Regional Government, if you don't agree, you have to give us recommendations, because a document has to be in sync. We make plans in advance, everything must be in sync. If the aspect that causes delays is more specifically on program activities that have not accommodated the Community interest, even though on the other hand the Regional Government also exists, maybe from a legislative perspective it is not enough, that's all.”

This informant's quote shows that the different orientations of the political communicator's interests greatly influenced the process of political communication that took place in the discussions on the West Sulawesi Revised APBD. The executive, in this case the Governor, has more connotations of the implementation of the Vision and Mission which are then actualized through the programs contained in the body of the revised APBD, but in reality, the DPRD consider that DPRD' programs are more optimal and Affect directly with the interests of the community.

“Basically, DPRD does not have a vision and mission, while the Regional Head has a vision and mission. Therefore, In defending the main thought, the DPRD must ensure that those are the activities that are proposed as part of the DPRD's efforts to achieve the Governor's vision and mission. It is an aspect of DPRD support, which strives for the achievement of the governor's vision and mission. We see that none of the 45 DPRD members are willing to sacrifice in order to accomplish a mission of service to the community, but we have to do that. We see and dissect the General budget policies – provisional budget priorities and

funding levels (KUA-PPAS). We see that there are programs that are out of sync. For example, the Governor's vision and mission is to reduce the poverty rate but the fact that the programs at the SKPD are not optimal in reducing the level of poverty, but through the main thoughts, we see various programs that can support the Governor's vision and mission.”

Based on the statement from the informant, it can be seen that the pattern of interests that is focused on the interests of the community is often realized differently, even though in the case studies, there is a joint agreement on regulatory aspects but there is still a narrative that overlaps with the effectiveness of the programs contained in the Body of the revised APBD which has been approved.

4. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that political communication between the executive and the legislature in discussing the revised APBD still has overlapping narratives regarding the effectiveness of the program in the revised regional budget (ABPD). Various quotations obtained from informants indicate that the pattern of interests centered on society's interests is actualized differently. What has been agreed upon further strengthens the notion that political communicators from the executive and the legislature have an orientation to political interests. These political interests significantly affect the efficiency of discussing the West Sulawesi Revised APBD.

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